

Supporting Information

Competition in Coordination Assemblies: 1D-Coordination Polymer or 2D-Nets Based on Co(NCS)2 and 4'-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3,2':6',3''-terpyridine

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Figure S1. Electrospray mass spectrum of **2**.

Figure S2. 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **2** (CDCl_3 , 298 K). * = CDCl_3 . See Scheme 2 for atom labelling.

Figure S3. NOESY spectrum of **2** (500 MHz ^1H NMR, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Figure S4. HMQC spectrum of **2** (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Figure S5. HMBC spectrum of **2** (500 MHz ^1H , 126 MHz $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$, CDCl_3 , 298 K).

Figure S6. Powder XRD pattern (295 K) of the bulk material from experiment I compared to that predicted from the single crystal structure (130 K) of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{MeOH})_2]_n$.

Figure S7. Powder XRD pattern (295 K) of the bulk material from experiment III compared to that predicted from the single crystal structure (130 K) of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{MeOH})_2]_n$.

Figure S8. Top: Overlay of the PXRD patterns from the powders obtained from the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 bulk reactions of $\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2$ and **2**. Middle and lower figures: Predicted powder patterns from the single crystal structures of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{MeOH})_2]_n$ and $[\{\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2\} \cdot 3\text{MeOH}]_n$.

Figure S9. Powder XRD pattern (295 K) of the bulk material from experiment II compared to those predicted from the single crystal structures (130 K) of $[\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{MeOH})_2]_n$, $[\{\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2\} \cdot 3\text{MeOH}]_n$ and $[\{\text{Co}(\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2\} \cdot 2.2\text{CHCl}_3]_n$.